

XXVII INTERNATIONAL
ECO-CONFERENCE®
27th-29th SEPTEMBER 2023

ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION
OF URBAN AND SUBURBAN
SETTLEMENTS

PROCEEDINGS

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PROCEEDINGS

NOVI SAD, SERBIA

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2023.

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of Novi Sad**

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Novi Sad**

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THE ECOLOGICAL MOVEMENT OF THE CITY OF NOVI SAD:

AN IMPORTANT DECISION OF ITS PROGRAMME COUNCIL

Since 1995, the Ecological Movement of the City of Novi Sad organizes „EcoConference® on Environmental Protection of Urban and Suburban Areas”, with international participation. Twelve biennial conferences have been held so far (in 1995, 1997, 1999, 2001, 2003, 2005, 2007, 2009, 2011, 2013, 2015, 2017, 2019, and 2021.).

Their programs included the following environmental topics:

Session 1: Environmental spheres: a) air, b) water, c) soil, d) biosphere

Session 2: Technical and technological aspects of environmental protection

Session 3: Sociological, health, cultural, educational and recreational aspects of environmental protection

Session 4: Economic aspects of environmental protection

Session 5: Legal aspects of environmental protection

Session 6: Ecological system projecting (informatics and computer applications in the field of integrated protection)

Session 7: Sustainable development of urban and suburban settlements ecological aspects

Conference participants have commended the scientific and organizational levels of the conferences. Conference evaluations have indicated that some aspects are missing in the conference program. In addition, since a team of conference organizers was completed, each even year between the conferences started to be viewed as an unnecessary lag in activity.

Eco-Conference® on Safe Food

With the above deliberations in mind, a decision was made that the Ecological Movement of the City of Novi Sad should embark on another project – the organization of Eco-Conferences® on Safe Food. These Conferences were planned to take place in each even year. Preparations for the first Eco-Conferences® on safe food started after the successful completion of the Eco-Conference® `99. So far ten Eco-Conferences® have been held (in 2000, 2002, 2004, 2006, 2008, 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016, 2018, 2020, and 2022.) focusing this general theme.

Theme of the Eco-Conference®

By organizing the Eco-Conference® on Safe Food, the organizer wishes to cover all factors that affect the quality of human living. Exchange of opinions and practical experiences should help in identifying and resolving the various problems associated with the production of safe food. Since 2007 Eco-Conference® gained five times in a row, a sponsorship from UN and their sectorial organizations (UNESCO and UN-FAO) and became purely scientific Conference.

Objectives of the Eco-Conference®

- To acquaint participants with current problems in the production of safe food.
- To make realistic assessments of the causes of ecological imbalance in the conventional agricultural production and the impact of various pollution sources on the current agricultural production.
- Based on an exchange of opinions and available research data, to make long-term strategic programs of developing an industrialized, controlled, integral, alternative and sustainable agriculture capable of supplying sufficient quantities of quality food, free of negative side effects on human health and the environment.

Basic Topics of the Eco- Conference®

Basic topics should cover all relevant aspects of the production of safe food. When defining the basic topics, the intention was to itemize the segments of the production of safe food as well as the related factors that may affect or that already have already been identified as detrimental for food safety and quality. The topics include ecological factors of safe food production, correct choice of seed (genetic) material, status and preparation of soil as the basic substrate for the production of food and feed, use of fertilizers and pesticides in integrated plant protection, use of biologicals, food processing technology, economic aspects, marketing and packaging of safe food. To paraphrase, the envisaged topics cover the production of safe food on the whole, individual aspects of the production and their mutual relations, and impact on food quality and safety.

Sessions of the Eco- Conference®

1. Climate and production of safe food.
2. Soil and water as the basis of agricultural production.
3. Genetics, genetic resources, breeding and genetic engineering in the function of producing safe food.
4. Fertilizers and fertilization practice in the function of producing safe food.
5. Integrated pest management and use of biologicals.
6. Agricultural production in view of sustainable development
7. Production of field and vegetable crops.
8. Production of fruits and grapes.
9. Livestock husbandry from the aspect of safe food production.
10. Processing of agricultural products in the framework of safe food production.
11. Economic aspects and marketing as segments of the production of safe food.

12. Food storage, transportation and packaging.
13. Nutritional food value and quality nutrition.
14. Legal aspects of protecting brand names of safe food.
15. Ecological models and software in production of safe food.

Attempts will be made to make the above conference program permanent. In this way will the conference become recognizable in form, topics and quality, which should help it find its place among similar conferences on organized elsewhere in the world.

By alternately organizing conferences on environmental protection of urban and suburban areas in odd years and conferences on safe food in even years, the Ecological Movement of the City of Novi Sad is completing its contribution to a higher quality of living of the population. Already in the 19th century, Novi Sad was a regional centre of social progress and broad-mindedness. Today, owing first of all to its being a university centre, Novi Sad is in the vanguard of ecological thought in this part of Europe.

It is our duty to work on the furtherance of the ecological programs of action and, by doing so, to make our contribution to the protection of the natural environment and spiritual heritage with the ultimate goal of helping the population attain a higher level of consciousness and a higher quality of living.

Director of the Ecological Movement of Novi Sad
Nikola Aleksic

CONTENT

THE ECOLOGICAL MOVEMENT OF THE CITY OF NOVI SAD: AN IMPORTANT DECISION OF ITS PROGRAMME COUNCIL	8
---	---

INTRODUCTORY PRESENTATION

<i>Božidar Kemić</i> GEOENGINEERING IN CROATIA AND THE REGION – ACTUAL CONTEXT, EVIDENCE AND IMPLICATIONS	19
<i>Vladan Joldžić</i> SOCIO-LEGAL ASPECTS OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN THE LIGHT OF THE UN AGENDA 2030.....	43
<i>Nikola Aleksić</i> GLOBAL PEACE	55

PARTS OF THE ENVIRONMENT

Air

<i>Jovana Džoljić, Vladimir Popović, Jovan Mišić</i> ROAD TRAFFIC IMPACT ON THE AIR QUALITY IN THE URBAN ENVIRONMENT	83
<i>Mirjana Anđelković Lukić, Milica Tomašević</i> FROM AIR SPA TO AIR POLLUTION – SURDULICA 2023.....	91
<i>Matija Milošević, Tijana Milanović, Anica Milošević, Gordana Bogdanović, Ljiljana Đorđević, Slađana Nedeljković</i> INFLUENCE OF AIR POLLUTION ON THE ENVIRONMENT AND HUMAN HEALTH.....	99

Water

<i>Velibor Spalević, Ronaldo Luiz Mincato, Paul Sestras, Branislav Dudić, Rastko Marković</i> FROM VULNERABLE TO GREEN LAND USE: CONTRIBUTION TO THE KNOWLEDGE OF WATERSHEDS RESILIENCE IN BERANE BASIN, MONTENEGRO	109
<i>Vera Popović, Ljubica Šarčević-Todosijević, Željka Đurišić, Vesna Gantner, Vladimir Filipović, Jelena Bošković, Aleksandar Stevanović, Nataša Ljubičić</i> THE SIGNIFICANCE OF AGROECOLOGY IN WATER AND SOIL PROTECTION	119
<i>Ivana Stanković, Jasna Grabić, Zorica Srđević, Pavel Benka</i> ASSESSMENT OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES, PRESSURES AND MEASURES IN THE GRADAC RIVER BASIN, SERBIA	127
<i>Miloš Pavlović, Svetlana Roljević Nikolić, Violeta Mickovski Stefanović, Mirela Matković Stojšin, Jovan Lazarević, Dragana Stanisavljević</i> INFLUENCE OF HIGH CONTENT OF HEAVY METALS IN WATER ON HUMAN HEALTH AND METHODS FOR CLEANING OF CONTAMINANTS	135
<i>Tijana Milanović, Matija Milošević, Gordana Bogdanović, Anica Milošević, Ljiljana Đorđević, Slađana Nedeljković</i> PLANTS AS INDICATORS OF WATER POLLUTION	143

Soil

<i>Željko Mihaljev, Milica Živkov Baloš, Sandra Jakšić, Marija Mihaljev, Nenad Popov</i> STATUS OF RADIONUCLIDES IN THE SOILS FROM VOJVODINA PROVINCE, NORTHERN SERBIA.....	155
---	-----

Biosphere

<i>Anja Đoković, Milena Lakićević</i> DENDROFLORA ANALYSIS OF THE OLD PARK IN TEMERIN.....	163
<i>Dragana Stanisavljević, Violeta Mickovski Stefanović, Jovan Ćirić, Predrag Ilić, Dragan Veličković</i> UTILIZATION POSSIBILITIES OF AGRICULTURAL WASTE AS ENERGY-VALUABLE RESOURCES	171
<i>Bratislav Lukić, Igor Milanović, Goran Petrović</i> THE IMPACT OF THE ADAPTIVE TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT SYSTEM ON THE PROTECTION OF THE ENVIRONMENT	179

<i>Radujica Rakić, Jela Ikanović, Vera Popović, Sveto Rakić, Vladica Ristić, Vesna Gantner, Ljubiša Kolarić</i>	
SECONDARY AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN FUNCTION OF RAW MATERIALS FOR FURTHER INDUSTRIAL PROCESSING	187

**SOCIAL, HEALTH, CULTURAL, EDUCATIONAL
AND RECREATIONAL ASPECTS OF PROTECTION**

Health

<i>V.V. Zakrevskii, A.A. Podorvanov, M.I. Kopchak</i>	
MINIMIZING THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF ORGANIC FOOD PRODUCTION	197

<i>Igor Stojanov, Ivan Pušić, Radomir Ratajac, Stevan Rodić, Aleksandar Milovanović</i>	
PREVENTIVE THERAPY OF DIROFILARIOSIS IN DOGS – INTRODUCTION TO ANTHELMINTIC RESISTANCE	205

Cultural Aspects of Protection

<i>Agota Vitkai Kucera</i>	
PRESERVATION OF THE MUSICAL CULTURE OF NOVI SAD	215

Educational Aspects of Protection

<i>Vera Virijević Mitrović</i>	
ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION FOR PRESCHOOLERS THROUGH ART	223

Social aspects of Protection

<i>Slobodan M. Filipović</i>	
ANCIENT SERBIAN SPIRITUAL CALENDAR.....	233

Recreational Aspects of Protection

<i>Nourelein Elmarsafy, Aleš Golja</i>	
INCLUSIVE NATURAL ENVIRONMENT FOR LEISURE AND RECREATION, (Study Case: Tivoli Landscape Park).....	247

Aleš Golja

BALANCING ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND OUTDOOR RECREATION: A SUSTAINABLE APPROACH.....	255
<i>Luka Čuš, Aleš Golja</i>	
REVITALISATION OF BROWNFIELDS FOR RECREATION AND LEISURE ACTIVITIES, (Study case: degradation area in the city of Ptuj)	263
<i>Iztok Novak</i>	
ADDRESSING PHYSICAL FITNESS AND ENVIRONMENTAL CONCERNS AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS	271
<i>Žiga Bratuž</i>	
OUTDOOR SPORT ACTIVITIES STUDENT ATTENDANCE TRENDS AT SOME OF THE FACULTIES OF UNIVERSITY OF LJUBLJANA	279
<i>Mbarek Alhaddar, Eva Erdelyi</i>	
ESSAOUIRA ATTRACTING MORE TOURISTS AS A SUSTAINABLE DESTINATION IN MOROCCO	285
<i>Annisa Husnul Latifah, Damla Bal, Éva Erdélyi</i>	
COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT IN CO-CREATING A SUSTAINABLE TOURISM MILIEU: LESSONS FROM INDONESIAN VILLAGES.....	293
<i>Shi Junfeng, Sándor Lőrincz, Éva Erdélyi</i>	
ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL TOURISTS' PERCEPTION OF SAFETY WHEN VISITING THE HUNGARIAN CAPITAL.....	303
ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF PROTECTION	
<i>Željko Grublješić, Miloš Jokić, Dragana B. Popović</i>	
INSTITUTIONAL DETERMINATION OF THE PUBLIC SECTOR WITH REFERENCE TO THE IMPORTANCE OF FINANCIAL REPORTING TO STATE AUTHORITIES ON THE ISSUE OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION	315
<i>Miloš Tubić, Miloš Dragosavac, Slavica Anđelić, Željko Grublješić, Ognjen Bakmaz</i>	
INFLUENCE OF FINANCIAL STABILITY ON ENVIRONMENTAL PROJECTS OF LOCAL COMMUNITIES.....	323
<i>Predrag Brković, Nikola Ćurčić, Violeta Mickovski Stefanović, Dragana Stanisavljević, Predrag Ilić</i>	
ECONOMICS OF THE FUTURE - GREEN ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	329

*Slavica Anđelić, Miloš Dragosavac, Miloš Tubić,
Željko Grublješić, Ognjen Bakmaz*
INTERNAL AUDIT IN THE MANAGEMENT SUPPORT SYSTEM
IN COMPANIES THAT HAVE ADOPTED THE ECONOMIC
ASPECT OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION337

*Milica Stanković, Tiana Anđelković,
Gordana Mrdak, Suzana Stojković*
TRANSITION TO GREEN ECONOMY AND GREEN JOBS343

Bojana Kovačević Berleković, Ana Jovičić Vuković, Tatjana Bošković
FOREST SELFNESS AS AN INNOVATIVE
TOURISM PRODUCT IN VOJVODINA351

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF URBAN AND SUBURBAN SETTLEMENTS – ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS

*Goran Skatarić, Velibor Spalević, Ronaldo Luiz Mincato,
Shuraik Kader, Branislav Dudić*
ENHANCING GREEN GROWTH AND CLIMATE RESILIENCE IN
MONTENEGRO: A CONTRIBUTION TO POLICY KNOWLEDGE359

Csaba Limbek, Zsuzsanna Tóth, Zolt Töröcsvári
GLOBAL CHALLENGES, LOCAL RESPONSES
ECO-VILLAGES IN HUNGARY369

*Dejan Zejak, Goran Skatarić, Marija Gavrilović,
Branislav Dudić, Velibor Spalević*
DRIVING GROWTH AND SUSTAINABILITY:
UNDERSTANDING THE STATE OF AGRICULTURAL
MACHINERY IN MONTENEGRO377

*Ljubica Šarčević-Todosijević, Kristina Vojvodić, Aleksandra Malivuk,
Marija Perić, Vera Popović, Jelena Golijan, Ljubiša Živanović*
ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION - THE LEADING
CHALLENGE OF THE 21ST CENTURY387

NAME REGISTRY395

Educational Aspects of Protection

ECO-CONFERENCE 2023

ECOLOGICAL MOVEMENT OF THE CITY OF NOVI SAD

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ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION FOR PRESCHOOLERS THROUGH ART

Abstract

The paper aims to present specifics of environmental education for preschoolers via art, in accordance with the modern concept of environmental art, the psychology of creativity, and child's play. Analogous to the modifications in contemporary ecological thought, from scientific positivism to aesthetic ecological paradigm, we approach early-age children's environmental education through art as an activity that incites the affective in a human being. Thus, we argue the expediency of introducing environmental art to the activities of preschool children as an indispensable method of setting environmental values in accordance with the emotional, cognitive, and ethical development of a child's personality.

Keywords: *environmental education, preschool age, environmental art*

INTRODUCTION

Studying the development of ecological thought for half a century now, we gain an insight into two main currents of ecological paradigm that have morphed in terms of progress in environmental philosophy, aesthetics, and activism. The original ecological paradigm, having sprung from the 19th-century scientific positivism whose main thought relied on harmonic relationships in untouched nature, was based on the methods of scientific-cognitive biology and other natural sciences, as well as the contemporary environmental paradigm that is convincingly relying on the findings of modern science of unstoppable, forceful flimsiness of the nature, unbalanced natural processes, the effects of which reflected in chaos (Simus, J. 2008, 63-79). As such, the contemporary environmental paradigm exhibits characteristics analogous to the properties of modern art, the aesthetic of contemporary artwork, which from the avant-garde

movements until this day are characterized by unsettledness and fluidity, aspirations guided by the psychological processes in the creator's personality, and sociological changes, upheavals even in the creator's societies that they themselves participate in, at times anticipating those changes in their artwork.

In this case, the subject of our study, therefore, is not context consideration of the environmental philosophy modern-day viewpoint, but, on the contrary, the link the environmental thought has with the effective pedagogy, i.e., environmental education of preschool children. Considering the following two factors 1) specifics of the psychological development of preschoolers, therefore, cognitive and emotional development at that age, and 2) particularities of the psychology of creativity, we will try to prove the hypothesis that the most appropriate method for in-depth and far-reaching development of environmental awareness among the youngest population, as well as setting value systems for the preservation of nature, is through the emotional, affective sphere – through art education and expression through practical activities in the field of eco-art for children.

SIMILARITY BETWEEN CHILD'S PLAY AND CREATIVITY

When it comes to the healthy development of the whole personality in early childhood, we give precedence to child's play. Play, as children's spontaneous activity, is charged with psychological and creative potential for the development of a versatile personality – namely, perception, motor skills, imagination, divergent and convergent thinking, problem-solving, empirical knowledge, resolving frustration, and when it comes to groups: social skills and relationship development, communication, bonding, empathy. In the school period, it is considered that the need for play subsides because it is replaced by other forms of activity, more self-aware and more rational attitudes. However, with creators, play is present throughout life; more precisely, the need for play from early childhood turns into creative activities at an older age that acquire their organized form and rules in adulthood. Art “leads to the system of reality, without abolishing the system of pleasure.” (Panic, V. 2012, 14.) In any case, children's play and the creative activity of an adult artist have important common features: they appear as spontaneous activity, in both sometimes there is curiosity and experimentation in the material; they have their own internal motivation – self-rewarding by enjoying the very act of playing, that is, creativity; release from frustration and stress. The value and goal of both types of activities is in that inner, emotional satisfaction and release.

In the psychology of a small child, similar to that of an adult artist, sometimes a destructive urge appears. Game and art activities lead to overcoming the need

for destruction, they gradually develop and nurture the will to build, combine and add to the resulting structures, often in continuations and over a longer period of time in which the created creation changes in the game or art activity, but at the same time it changes and builds. the child's personality: ability for combinatorics, sense of space, patience and will, constructive qualities, self-confidence.

Younger children are in many creative abilities, according to Vladislav Panic's creativity psychology, "superior to older children – in drawing, spontaneous and collective activities, symbolic expression" (Panic, 2012, 69). The development of creative abilities at a younger age (up to the age of 6) is somewhat faster than the development of intelligence. Syncretic thinking, the ability of symbolic representation, the inner motivation of play, united by the omnipotence of preschool children – ignorance of their own limitations, represent favorable preconditions for their active and happy participation in independent and collective activities in the field of eco-art. For this reason, it is necessary to base environmental education in preschool age on children's spontaneous play and ability to express themselves creatively and solve problems. Environmental education through art corresponds and relies especially on affectivity, play activities and children's creativity.

ENVIRONMENTAL ART

Environmental art, art in nature, is an umbrella term for the art of spatial interventions or installations in the natural environment that refers to the principle that materials and methods utilized to put up installations within the environment do not affect it whatsoever. Similar to this notion is also the one of land art, earth art, where large-scale installations are made to create a unique whole with the landscape, such as the famous Spiral Jetty by Robert Smithson. Yet, sometimes land art creations are smaller-scale, fragile, subtle structures; additionally, ecological art pieces that resemble natural self-contained structures are most likely short-lived, crumbling under the slightest atmospheric shift, the case being certain landscape installations made of twigs, ice, or leaves by the British land artist Andy Goldsworthy.

In addition to natural materials, which are subject to short life and decomposition, so that they do not leave a trace or pollution in nature, in some pieces of eco-art recycled material is used, which draws the public's attention to the accumulation of inorganic waste and often the lack or inconsistencies in its disposal and recycle. Provocative works of eco-art created from plastic bottles talk about the accumulation of plastic waste in rivers and on wild landfills in Serbia, such as the *Portrait of Jovan Memedovic*, the street artist Pianist.

In philosophy of art, a bridge is established: creator-artwork-recipient, i.e. audience. Each work of art creates a communication bridge with its observers, contemporaries, through its artistic values and specific content, and in the case of

great and significant artistic achievements, this link is permanent, they are timeless, they communicate with the audience, stimulating different questions and answers, interpretations and emotions even centuries after they arose. In the case of environmental art, which aims to arouse people's feelings related to respect for nature with its artistic interventions in the landscape, social involvement appears as an inevitable, default aspect of this form of art. It exists as a specific type of environmental activism; not as a socially beneficial action or a classic protest, but as an aesthetically shaped object, sculpture, installation or intervention in the landscape and at the same time a public, documented gesture of an artist who wants to draw attention to current global or local environmental problems in an original way, using the universal language of art .

ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION FOR PRESCHOOLERS

In terms of intensity and significance, the preschool period is decisive in forming a child's personality in many aspects, one of which is the child's system of values. Many sociological studies have explored the acceptance and foundation of a child's relationship with nature and environmental protection, stating that a child's attitude towards them is established through the media, in educational institutions, and within peer groups, but when it comes to an early age, predominantly in the family. Environmentally conscious parents will raise environmentally conscious children, through conversations and a personal example. Feelings of love and the need to identify with parents are fertile ground for building a child's sincere and deep feeling of love for nature. At the same time, we emphasize the importance of direct contact with nature and staying in it: "An emotional relationship cannot develop without a direct experience of the environment. Children must not only learn about the environment, but also experience it, and in order to achieve this, they must make contact with nature and become aware that they are part of it." (Markovic, M. 2017, 130) Overprotected children as well as children who to the extent that they spend time in an urban environment, indoors, in playrooms, exercise rooms or in front of screens, are deprived of the possibility of a spontaneous emotional response to the perception of the natural environment, a personal experience of being in it. Despite technological progress and the opportunities provided by the standard of living in an urban environment, the alienation of children from nature and instead of an empirical, virtual approach to knowledge, is becoming a burning problem of modern society. The role of the family is of crucial importance because "above all, it provides its younger members with the opportunity to emotionally experience and adopt a relationship with the values of the environment more than they can understand the needs of protection." (Markovic, M. 2017, 127-128)

The influence of kindergartens in the Republic of Serbia in the formation of environmental awareness among children is unbalanced in terms of its

constituents, because more work is done on the development of cognitive rather than emotional aspects of children's personality. The basic constituents of ecological awareness are: rational, value-based, emotional and voluntary (Kundacina, M. 1997. 47.) The role of kindergartens and teachers in ecological education has so far been mainly limited to acquiring the child's first knowledge about ecosystems and relationships in them, adopting respect for all living beings and accepting examples of desirable behavior in concrete situations (Kamenov, E. 2004. 23.)

The role of the social community in environmental education is not negligible; active participation of children in social events of environmental content is desirable at all ages. In this case, educators are invited to influence the development of constructive habits in children: from the idea to the realization of an eco-project that will make them useful members of an environmentally conscious society in the future, capable of effectively influencing the implementation and realization of sustainable systems. "The goal of ecological education is achieved when unity between ecological knowledge, ecological awareness and ecological practical action and behavior" (Jovanovic, B. according to Minic, V. 2020. 232.)

ECO-ART IN ACTIVITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Concrete performance of children's art activities based on ecological art, most often take place under the guidance of preschool teachers, sometimes artists of this field, outdoors, and most often concern the use of waste and recycled materials. Predominant are the principles of obviousness and the method of practical work.

Children themselves, spontaneously, without the guidance of adults, create out of nothing, more precisely, they turn the shapes and materials they find into a means of play. The benefits that these activities bring make them healthy from the point of view of the psychology of creativity, about which Vladislav Panic writes: "Games with different types of material are characteristic for a child. This is where manipulative and constructive abilities are developed. And not only them. This kind of diverse material that the child can freely shape and arrange is better for the development of creative dispositions than ready-made toys that children must not "spoil". The child can use these various materials for various purposes and to concretize various ideas. This is how imagination develops, the ability to combine, construct, and gets used to more diverse and freer meanings. Thus, children, in that period and in that way, start many creative works that they realize later in life." (Panic, V. 2012. 73.)

A positive example of eco-art for preschool children comes from the research of the Scandinavian land-artist and pedagogue Ingunn Solberg, who spent several weeks staying with children aged three to six in a kindergarten in nature, in a

coniferous forest during the winter. She initiated, proposed, participated, observed and described group land-art activities of children in a natural environment. According to the standards and national frameworks for raising preschool children in Norway, it is explicitly suggested that children should be co-creators and active participants in the formation of culture and the expression of cultural content. She used all aspects of being in nature to arouse children's sensations and creative mood towards land-art forms and activities. (Solberg, I. 2016. 5-6.) The tendencies of dealing with environmental art for children in the world framework are that renowned artists of land art and environmental art are often invited as leaders and initiators of activities so that they share their creative approach and attitudes about nature through joint project with children.

Staying in kindergarten in nature, except in Scandinavia, has become a practice in many developed countries of the world. In Italy and Japan, there are kindergartens that are architecturally connected to the forest, or those where the architectural solutions are such that from the functionally organized interior, children can immediately, by using a slide or removing a movable glass wall, find themselves outside, under the tree canopy, on the playground, in contact with the ground and grass.

Land-art, or earth art, implies a long stay in nature and direct contact with the earth, soil; collection and reorganization of natural material: branches, fruits, stones, etc. in a certain order, sometimes digging and playing in mud, snow, dry leaves, stream. According to the results of research by Finnish microbiologists and immunologists, (Roslund, M. et al. 2020) it turns out that contact with the soil is very important for strengthening the child's immunity and general psychophysical health. Other factors, apart from the microbiological composition of the soil, have an impact on health and psychophysical development in land-art games that contribute, such as shaping the earth, mud or sand, to stress relief, but also to strengthening motor skills, developing spatial intelligence and combinatorics (Virijevec Mitrovic , M. 2022. 226.)

Land-art games, apart from the mentioned advantages of being in nature and touching natural materials, structures and the living world, according to research by Virijevec Mitrovic, contribute to the development of inventiveness and overall progress in children's artistic expression. An additional value is working in a group and developing the social aspects of a child's personality: "A great contribution to the healthy psychological development of the personality and the development of positive emotions, support, empathy, trust, togetherness and the ability to share (both tasks and success) is an additional quality and never sufficiently used potential of all group activities of children, especially collective art activities and works." (Virijevec Mitrovic, 2022. 227.)

Pedagogues all over the world agree about the necessity to establish an ecological education program in educational institutions, which is implemented through the Green Planet program (Kamenov, 2004). However, there is still a lack

of appropriate “methodology for acquiring ecological culture aligned with psychological knowledge about specific ways of children's learning and experiencing the world around them” (Goleman, 2009. 25.) If we combine internal motivation in mastering new art creations and new aesthetic and ethical values associated with children's play, in the field of environmental education we could as well rely on children's play as the best way of experiential learning, even more as a spontaneous approach to art activities in shaping discarded materials and materials from nature. We can fully count on the mentioned positive experiences of organizing and implementing art activities with children in the area of land art and ecological art. Given that they respect the principle of discovery and spontaneity as in children's play activities, as well as enjoyment of the act itself and the rules that children set in the game, we can rely on children as collaborators and creators of these art works. A child's love for play, creativity and nature is a universal principle that guides us in performing ecological art with preschool children.

CONCLUSION

This research starts with the assumption that the environmental education of preschoolers starts with familiarization with the basic knowledge of the mutual relationship among all living creatures on the planet and human responsibility towards the environment, but the child's emotional and ethical relationship with nature can develop through ecological art. A preschooler's static attitude to what they know about relationships in nature has more to do with the original, now obsolete ecological paradigm sprouting from scientific positivism of the 19th century that simply cannot keep up with the rapid and dramatic changes in the modern world's ecosystems, determined by constant morphing of nature, and a strained relationship between the nature and humans. Approaching and influencing the contemporary ecological paradigm is viable through modern art, which, aside from the universal art language, is quite expectedly also conceptual, provocative, directed at the community, i. e. communicative, open for important questions. Modern art, being emotional and expressive, is quite analogous to a preschool child. Children's art, characterized by free play with materials, focused on eco-art, is a perfect tool for building and permanent acceptance of environmental awareness and activism at an early age. Intense as it is at the preschool age, with its own types of understanding of oneself and the world, the emotional and cognitive development of children should be linked to children's divergent, original creativity acts, which are the most potent at the preschool age. That being said, we can conclude that introducing environmental education into the preschool program in kindergartens involves the constant practice of environmental art and land art, with children inevitably spending time in nature.

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EKOLOŠKO VASPITANJE DECE PREDŠKOLSKOG UZRASTA KROZ UMETNOST

Apstrakt

Ovaj rad ima za cilj da predstavi specifičnosti ekološkog vaspitanja dece predškolskog uzrasta putem umetnosti u skladu sa savremenim konceptom ekološke misli. Ekološka paradigma preobratala se od naučnog pozitivizma ka estetskoj paradigmi o disbalansu u prirodi i stalnim promenama koje imaju svoju paralelu u savremenoj umetnosti. Analogno promenama u savremenoj ekološkoj misli, prilazimo ekološkom vaspitanju dece ranog uzrasta kroz koncept vaspitanja putem umetnosti kao delatnosti koja se obraća afektivnom u čoveku. Time argumentujemo svrsishodnost uvođenja ekološke umetnosti u aktivnosti

predškolske dece kao nezamenljivog načina prihvatanja ekoloških vrednosti u skladu sa emocionalnim, kognitivnim i etičkim razvojem dečje ličnosti.

Ključne reči: *ekološko vaspitanje, predškolski uzrast, ekološka umetnost*

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